

Table S1: Description of severe traumatic brain injury patients included in the study with Glasgow coma scale (GCS) score at admission and discharge and Glasgow outcome scale (GOS) score three months after discharge

Patient	Age	Gender	Mechanism of injury	GCS at admission	GCS at discharge	GOS three months after discharge	Intracranial pathology
1	73	M	motor vehicle accident	3	15	3	diffuse axonal injury (DAI)
2	71	F	fall	3	exitus letalis	1	subdural haematoma (SDH), subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH), intracerebral haematoma (ICH)
3	68	M	fall from height	6	exitus letalis	1	SAH
4	24	M	motor vehicle accident	5	15	5	DAI

Figure S1: Representative AFM image 10 x 10 μm applied for size distribution analysis of EV pool

Figure S2: Zeta potential of EV pool obtained by TRPS with nanopore NP400 with marked value

Figure S3: Possible artefacts obtained by cryo-TEM, which are attributed to ice contamination